

THE IMPORTANCE OF HAVING CONFIDENCE IN IELTS SPEAKING AND DEVELOPING IT STEP BY STEP

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Abstract. The article mainly analyzes the importance of having confidence in the IELTS speaking exam and how to form this confidence before the exam, and some practical research is done and emphasis is placed on improving the speech accuracy of language knowledge. It also provides clear information and personal views on why self-confidence is important. The article is also a useful guide for teachers in increasing students' self-confidence in improving their speaking skills. The ideas are proven by the clear views of the authors.

Key words: fluency, IELTS candidates, practice, positive attitude, right approaches, analytical skills, band descriptors, criteria;

Аннотация. В статье в основном анализируется важность уверенности в устной речи на экзамене IELTS и способы формирования этой уверенности перед экзаменом, а также проводятся некоторые практические исследования, и делается акцент на повышении точности речи языковых знаний. Он также предоставляет четкую информацию и личные взгляды на то, почему важна уверенность в себе. Статья также является полезным руководством для учителей по повышению уверенности учащихся в улучшении их навыков говорения. Идеи подтверждаются четкими взглядами авторов.

Ключевые слова: беглость, кандидаты IELTS, практика, позитивный настрой, правильные подходы, аналитические способности, дескрипторы бэндов, критерии;

Annotatsiya. Maqolada, asosan, IELTS so'zlashuv imtihonida ishonchga ega bo'lish muhimligi va bu ishonchni imtihon oldidan qanday shakllantirish kerakligi tahlil qilinadi va

ba'zi amaliy tadqiqotlar olib borilib, til bilimining nutq aniqligini oshirishga e'tibor qaratilgan. Shuningdek, u o'ziga ishonch nima uchun muhimligi haqida aniq ma'lumot va shaxsiy qarashlarni beradi. Maqola, shuningdek, o'quvchilarning nutq mahoratini oshirishda o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshirishda o'qituvchilar uchun foydali qo'llanma. Fikrlar mualliflarning aniq qarashlari bilan tasdiqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: ravonlik, IELTS nomzodlari, amaliyot, ijobiy munosabat, to'g'ri yondashuvlar, analitik ko'nikmalar, band deskriptorlari, mezonlar;

Introduction.

It is crystal clear that IELTS (International English Language Testing System) not only tests language skills of the candidates, but also their ability to show their analytical skills. These skills mainly play a great role in IELTS speaking as speaking itself is a productive skill. Also, it's considered output ability which demands to product oral speech consistent with knowledge and worldview of speaker. Therefore, it is natural that in order to have and develop excellent speaking skills one should work on their critical thinking abilities, and most importantly, after having developed these skills, they become stepping stone of one's speaking. So, how is this connected with having confidence? This paper answers to this exact question.

I believe that every English teacher have their own strategies of boosting students' speaking skills and my strategy on this matter is directly connected with affecting students' psychology by developing confidence, as I assume that confidence is the core of every action they do and every word they produce and below I will describe it on a broad basis and give examples of enhancing confidence while speaking.

Main part.

Having confidence while speaking undoubtedly has a number of merits. First of all, let's take a look at meaning of the word "CONFIDENCE". According to Oxford Languages and Google, it means "the feeling or belief that one can have faith in or rely on someone or something". [Oxford Languages, 2022]; This can apply to a variety of situations, such as

taking the IELTS exam. Being confident in your ability to pass the IELTS exam involves believing in yourself and understanding that you have the strength and ability to obtain your desired score. Additionally, IELTS Podcast channel also shows the importance of confidence by this: "Because you doubt what you are saying a lot less - so you sound more fluent. You probably speak a little louder - making it easier for you to be understood. You may be more expressive with your body language - again making it easier to understand you". [3]; As well, the reason why confidence can be a big driving factor in the exam is because a confident candidate does better than an unconfident candidate does.

To provide the finest answers possible, one must be confident during the exam. Confidence can assist people in speaking clearly and authoritatively. This may aid in the comprehension and response to your message by your target audience. I would say that all the assessment criteria given on the public band descriptors can be improved by improving confidence. Initially, for Fluency & Cohesion section, confidence makes an exam taker speak at normal pace without being too slow or too fast. In the second criteria, we can see that Lexical Resources should be used with the right approach at the right time to make the best out of it. So, the connection LR and confidence have together is that confidence calms down a person, through which one can think better. Naturally, when one thinks better, one can use better the necessary words instead of making irrational choice of words and speaking whatever stays in the tongue. Thirdly, preventing nervousness during the exam with confidence can assist candidates to produce a wide range of grammatical sentences and accurate structure with only few slips consistently in Grammatical Range and Accuracy section. Finally, in the Pronunciation criteria, one can mispronounce words due to being hurried which comes by feeling insecure during the exam. I believe that these all mentioned clearly presents the pivotal essentiality of being confident on the exam day.

However, how can one become confident and then, enter the exam room. Actually, there are hundreds of tips and strategies about it both by senior IELTS candidates and IELTS experts. Observing and studying all of them, I also came up with several strategies and stages for developing confidence beforehand the exam.

1. Having positive attitude

It is almost impossible to explain that how much does it mean to be positive about the exam and keeping that positive attitude on the exam day. Most people fail the exam, because they solely think of the possible negativities they can face instead of imagining positive things happening. Changing their attitudes to positive ones can change a course of events that happens, at least, this can give a smile to the face of the exam taker. But most importantly, positive attitude gives the candidate a muscle of confidence on the exam day.

2. Asking reliable sources

According to Ashley Fisher, one of the famous IELTS experts: "This is closely related to being prepared for the IELTS exam. If you have any questions about what you've read, seen, or heard, ask your teacher, tutor, or your local IELTS office. Going to a reliable source will make you feel more confident about the answer". Thus, having knowledge is a key factor on the test day. [Ashley Fisher, 2017];

3. Practice

The best sense of confidence comes through practice. Once candidates get used to practice consistently, they start to improve and develop confidence. And literally, the best sense of confidence is the confidence that was practiced for a long time. Through practice, students will be able to identify their weak and strong areas in the speaking, so that they can improve both of them.

Above given confidence-boosting approaches in increasing speaking skills, surely, all of them are effective and mostly used by high band score candidates. It helps not only to develop clear speech but also encourage students be happy themselves and make a choice on issues.

Conclusion. Before mentioned there's an enormous role of confidence in the IELTS speaking exam, which most people do not talk about. Having and developing confidence will have far reaching positive outcomes for the language learners and can pave away for effective communication by developing fluency, accuracy, pronunciation of the learners'.

Moreover, knowing about the effective confidence-boosting skills also will inspire teachers to be creative to enhance their students' speaking in general. In one word, confidence let exam takers be more peaceful, have clear speech, and think in a realistic way.

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